

THEORY, RESEARCH AND PRACTICE IN EUROPEAN CONTEXT

PRAGUE 14TH - 15TH SEPTEMBER 2023

H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 Project no. 101027291 Encounter: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships
Faculty of Humanities, Charles University in Prague, the Czech Republic

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

PRE-CONFERENCE EVENING

18:00-21:00

Pre-conference informal social meet-up

VENUE:

Náplavka Smíchov, Details TBC

CONFERENCE DAY 1

8:30-8:50

REGISTRATION, Coffee and Tea

8:50-9:00

Conference opening

9:00-10:15

KEYNOTE 1: Prof. Kay Tisdal

10:15-10:45

COFFEE BREAK

10:45-12:15

Parallel sessions 1

12:15-13:00

LIGHT LUNCH (POSTERS PRESENTATION)

13:00-14:30

Parallel sessions 2

14:30-15:00

Coffee break

15:00-16:15

KEYNOTE 2: Prof. Marek Tesar

16:15-17:45

Parallel session 3

17:45-18:00

Day 1 Closure

18:00-19:30

(optional): TOUR AROUND PRAGUE WITH GUIDE

Meet-up outside the building A, Hybernská 4

from 19:30

CONFERENCE SOCIAL DINNER

(VENUE: Gallery Hollar, Smetanovo nábřeží)

CONFERENCE DAY 2

8:00-8:55

REGISTRATION

9:00-9:15

Conference opening Day 2

9:15-10:30

KEYNOTE 3: Dr. Lenka Vochovcova

10:30-10:45

COFFEE BREAK

10:45-12:00

KEYNOTE 4: Prof. Michal Molcho

12:00-12:30

LIGHT LUNCH (POSTERS PRESENTATION)

12:30-14:00

Parallel session 4

14:00-14:30

Conference closure

PARALEL SESSIONS: PRESENTATIONS

PARALEL SESSION 1 (DAY 1; 10:45–12:15)

PS 1.1.

- 1.1.1. *John Potter & Michelle Cannon*: Partnership and empowerment in research practice with children
- 1.1.2. *Karin Osvaldsson Cromdal, Jacob Cromdal & Daniel Persson-Thunqvist*: Agency and ambiguity in young children's emergency calls
- 1.1.3. *Patricio Cuevas-Parra*: Child-led research: Strengthening children's voice, empowerment and agency

PS 1.2. SYMPOSIUM

- 1.2.1. *Sándor Pálfi*: Listening and hearing children's voices through rights based pedagogic practice
- 1.2.2. *Eleonora Teszenyi*: Representing and interpreting children's voice through an arts-based platform
- 1.2.3. *Natalie Canning*: Acknowledging children's rights as a process to empowerment

PS 1.3.

- 1.3.1. *Helena Szewiola*: Children in public space
- 1.3.2. *Denisa Kollarova*: Playground potentials: Tools of imagination
- 1.3.3. *Molly Brooks*: Urban livability and well-being: An evidence based approach to young peoples participation in research and creating change

PARALEL SESSIONS 2 (DAY 1; 13:00–14:30)

PS 2.1.

- 2.1.1. *Maria Manuel Vieira & Lia Pappámikail*: Gaining access and cooperation: Some methodological challenges in research with adolescents
- 2.1.2. *Letizia Luini*: Photo-production during research processes with children: free expression and participatory possibilities through photovoice
- 2.1.3. *Sheila Garrity, Monika Haid & Aidan Harte*: Spaces and Traces Young children's meaning making through digital methodologies in a time of global pandemic

PS 2.2.

- 2.2.1. *Pierangelo Barone, Camilla Barbanti, Veronica Berni & Monica Facciocchi*: Speaking up through research, taking the floor in society: a participatory research study on the impact of the theatre laboratory at the "Cesare Beccaria" youth detention center in Milan
- 2.2.2. *Ashley Woodfall*: Who Do You Want to Be? Participatory Creative Method in a Study in to Children's Media and Aspirations

PARALEL SESSIONS 3 (DAY 1; 16:15–17:45)

PS 3.1.

- 3.1.1. *Anezka Kuzmicova & Karolina Simkova*: Children thinking about facts via nonfiction book design
- 3.1.2. *Natascia Micheli*: Theological intelligence and learning in adolescents
- 3.1.3. *Lydie Kárníková & Karolína Šimková*: Young activists' perspectives on how society views their civic engagement in the online space

PS 3.2.

- 3.2.1. *Ruth Barnes*: Exploring children's wellbeing and the concept of 'generagency' in sport: a youth sports case study
- 3.2.2. *Sonja Arndt, Kylie Smith & Nicola Yelland*: Conceptualising 'the migrant child': Feminist, poststructural and posthuman speculations
- 3.2.3. *Leila Angod*: Conceptualizing "voice" in school - based youth participatory action research: Constraints and new possibilities in anti-racism research

PS 3.3. WORKSHOP

Agnieszka Krzyżak-Pitura, Helena Szewiola, Beata Patuszyńska & Gooitske Zijlstra: "Towards Child-Friendly Cities: The Importance of Inclusive Urban Space Design and its Impact on Children's Well-being"

PARALEL SESSIONS 4 (DAY 2; 12:30–14:00)

PS 4.1.

- 4.1.1. *Beata Patuszynska*: Empowering children through co-creation. Case study of writing a book with and for children about their first steps into urban independence
- 4.1.2. *Grace Spencer & Jill Thomson*: Problematizing empowerment: unpacking young African migrants' concepts of power and empowerment - implications for youth agency in the European context
- 4.1.3. *Jacob Cromdal, Sally Wiggins & Annerose Willemsen*: Food for fantasy: Sharing imaginary worlds during preschool meals

PS 4.2.

- 4.2.1. *Laura Migliorini, Martina Olcese & Paola Cardinali*: Wellbeing, engagement with community settings and deprivation: A comparison between school-aged children with different ethnic backgrounds
- 4.2.2. *Alexandra König, Jessica Schwittek & Katarzyna Jendrzey*: The Child as an Agent in Transnational Families - Methodological and Theoretical Considerations Using the Example of a Polish-German Research Project
- 4.2.3. *Kwon Minkyung*: Teenage girls navigating and challenging the contradictory construction of a 'girl-child': a theoretical contribution of 'childism'

POSTERS

- Sara Filipiak & Beata Łubianka*: Locus of control in adolescents with different levels of neuroticism
- Beata Łubianka & Sara Filipiak*: Youth perspectives for hope for success in a Polish sample
- Markéta Michalčová & Tereza J. Brumovská*: Youth's perceptions of support and empowerment from digital heroes and imaginary friends in daily experiences
- Eilidh Lamb*: Creating spaces for children to be seen and heard: Developing arts-based research methods for engagement with young people and their understandings of space in the new Bairns Hoose (Barnahus) in Scotland